

A Practical Application of a Dataset Analysis in an Intrusion Detection System

Diego Fernandez*, Laura Vigoya*, Fidel Cacheda*, Francisco J. Novoa*, Manuel F. Lopez-Vizcaino[†] and Victor Carneiro*

*University of A Coruna

Campus de Elvina, s/n

15071, A Coruna, Spain

Email: diego.fernandez, l.v.vigoya, fidel, fjnova, viccar@udc.es

[†]University of A Coruna, CITIC

Campus de Elvina, s/n

15071, A Coruna, Spain

Email: manuel.fernandezl@udc.es

Abstract—Intrusion detection systems try to identify unauthorized use, misuse and abuse in computer networks. We can use different kinds of algorithms to detect intrusive activities, but their success mainly lies in the quality of the data that they operate on. In many cases, the algorithms do not obtain the expected results. This happens in many scenarios because there is not a data processing step previous to applying the algorithms.

In this paper a systematic analysis of a public intrusion detection dataset has been developed in order to overcome the mentioned shortcomings and understand how the traffic behaves in this particular context and how flows actually perform on the network. So, this analysis is used for avoiding common pitfalls introduced because of a misunderstanding of data peculiarities and for selecting and tailoring correctly the algorithms. Specifically, we have employed machine learning algorithms to classify the traffic into normal and attack flows.

In addition, it is important to decide what features should be evaluated. Typically standard metrics employed to measure the correctness in the classification do not take into account time to make the decision, what is essential in an intrusion detection system. This is the reason why we introduce a metric that considers both the accuracy and the delay to make the decision and that is employed for evaluating machine learning algorithms in other domains.

The conclusions obtained from our dataset analysis can be used to develop new models that could fit the data better than existing approaches.

Index Terms—intrusion detection systems, analysis, metric, algorithm design, computer network management

I. INTRODUCTION

Network monitoring becomes an essential part of systems security to control its proper work and to detect possible security issues [26][13]. Bace and Mell define intrusions as attempts to compromise the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of a computer or network, or to bypass the security mechanisms of a computer or network [3]. According to this, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) provide a method to discover attacks or anomalous situations based on communication networks content. However, as a result of the exponential increase of connected devices and the traffic generated, classical analysis techniques based on payload packet inspection

become unfeasible, due to the high amount of time and resources consumed by these methods [24].

Other less resource-intensive alternatives have appeared to complement the packet inspection. For instance, the flow-based monitoring is increasingly used in enterprise and home networks. In fact, flow data can be employed not only for network management [22], but also for anomaly detection, traffic classification [2] or IDS [20], [11]. In this work we have opted for this alternative.

In addition, there are two different approaches in IDS depending on the location of the detection system. If it is placed on each host to be supervised, they are called Host-based IDS or HIDS. However, systems that survey network communications are called Network-based IDS or NIDS, and these are the ones under study in this article.

Techniques used in the field of anomaly-based IDS could be classified into three big groups [7]: statistic based, knowledge based and machine learning based. Among the machine-learning techniques Random Forest (RF) is very popular.

In this paper we delve into the ISCX dataset in order to analyze the behavior of different features available. Then we propose a RF model taking into account the information obtained from the analysis. This RF receives flow information generated by a Self-Organizing Map (SOM), which creates clusters (or superflows) formed by similar flows. The model is used in a binary classification problem, aiming at determining whether a superflow is formed by attack flows as soon as possible. In the evaluation process, apart from traditional metrics, we propose the use of a metric initially designed for early risk detection in other domain.

The structure of the article is as follows. In Section II we comment the state of the art. Then, we present a deep analysis of the data employed. Next we describe the model and the features. Section VI details the configuration settings, how the experiments have been performed and the results obtained. Finally, we expose our conclusion and the future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Applications of RF in IDS have been widely employed. Authors in [19] survey 35 RF based methods for IDS focused on network intrusions. The majority of works studied use RF models as classifiers; however, there are other non-obvious applications, such as feature selection. The papers are compared based on the following parameters: detection strategy type, problem domain, main use, parameters for the RF model, software architecture, feature selection approach, number of selected features, datasets on tests, metrics on tests, and the main achieved results.

Among the RF algorithms applied to IDS, Yin et al. [25] propose a high-speed intrusion detection approach based on the non-extensive Tsallis entropy, for feature extraction, and two RF models for classification to enhance the performance. The proposed anomaly detection method can achieve competitive detection accuracy with a high recall.

Hota and Shrivastava [9] evaluated five classifiers over the NSL-KDD dataset in two different viewpoints. First, the classification techniques are applied for a two class problem as binary classification (normal and attack), and second, it is applied for a five class problem as multiclass classification. RF with 15 selected features achieved the best results in both cases.

Additionally, Masarat et al. [17] present a parallel RF algorithm for network intrusion detection. They studied the weaknesses in RF algorithms and propose solutions for them. The differences from the conventional RF are the following: (i) on each node, the selected variable to make the split is taken from a roulette wheel weighted using the Information Gain values; (ii) a fuzzy logic is implemented on the RF output combining the classifier result, the detection rates, and a misclassification cost matrix. In the presented evaluation over the KDD99 dataset, the approach provides an accuracy of 94.4%.

On the other hand, SOMs are powerful unsupervised neural networks that provide simultaneous clustering and dimensionality reduction through the projection of a dataset into a two-dimensional lattice of neurons [5]. This technique allows performing clustering as well as dimensionality reduction by means of the projection of input data into a neuron grid, where each neuron is linked to its neighbors preserving input topology. This property makes easier data exploration and the discovery of particularities related to input data.

There are some experiments based on SOM for IDS. Pachghare et al. [18] introduced the SOM for IDS, explaining the system architecture, and figuring out the advantages and disadvantages of SOM and indicating how it is useful for building an IDS. In Ibrahim et al. [16] authors studied and analyzed the performance of a SOM, when implemented as part of an IDS, to detect anomalies on acknowledge discovery in KDD 99 and NSL-KDD datasets. Other authors [10] proposed an IDS based on hierarchical approach that integrates a RF based misuse detection model and a SOM based anomaly detection model with low computational cost. The RF model

is used as a misuse detection module and the SOM model is used as an anomaly detection module. The network traffic is firstly classified using the RF model and the known attacks are then detected at this stage. The traffic classified as normal in the first stage is submitted to the SOM model, which points out the outliers as attacks.

In addition, it is important to decide what features should be evaluated. Feature engineering plays a vital role in big data analytics since machine learning and data mining algorithms cannot work without data. Little can be achieved if there are few features to represent the underlying data objects, and the quality of results of those algorithms largely depends on the quality of the available features [6]. In addition it is not important the way of a feature is implemented, and therefore multiple implementations may be possible [23].

Feature engineering has been extensively studied by the machine learning community under various headings. In networks, the conventional paradigm for generating features for nodes is based on feature extraction techniques which typically involve some seed hand-crafted features based on network properties [8].

Typically, standard metrics are employed to measure the correctness in the classification. However, they do not take into account time to make the decision, what is essential in an IDS. In [19] they point out that the basic and useful metrics to provide an acceptable understanding about the performance of intrusion detection approaches used are detection rate (DR), false positive rate (FPR), and the area under the curve (AUC). However, they observe that the metric DR may not be representative for IDS when considering the impact of threats. In this context, we consider the Early Risk Detection Error (ERDE), presented by Losada et al. [15], as a promising metric. This metric has been applied to linguistic pattern domains.

III. ANALYSIS

UNB ISCX is a synthetic and labeled dataset generated by the Cybersecurity Institute of Canada. It is a well known dataset for Intrusion Detection research in communication networks [21]. This dataset consist of a seven days network activity with attacks distributed through this period. It has a wide diversity of intrusion scenarios (for instance, HTTP DoS or Brute Force SSH). We used the flow set generated with these data to obtain the features. Flows are labeled pointing out if the flow is part of an attack or it represents normal traffic. From the original dataset, a feature selection has been performed.

Some features have been taken into account to represent network traffic information. We perform the analysis over TCP, UDP and ICMP traffic, classified in attack and normal. Under these properties, 1,928,942 flows were used. The anomalous traffic consists of 68,791 flows, which represents the 3.535% of data used for analysis. The details of the number of flows found by day, protocol and tag (normal/attack) are described in Table I.

TABLE I
FLOWS STATISTICS.

Day	TCP		UDP		ICMP		Flows
	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	
Friday	0	272	0	41	0	0	313
Saturday	2082	92832	0	37945	0	81	132940
Sunday	20061	200995	58	54037	240	134	275525
Monday	3715	118529	0	48465	55	572	171336
Tuesday	37377	404232	1	123970	0	6058	571638
Wednesday	0	434571	0	87062	0	513	522146
Thursday	5202	203122	0	46449	0	271	255044
Total	68437	1454553	59	397969	295	7629	1928942

For the generation of the dataset, with the aim of imitating the actions of malicious users, four scenarios of multi-stage attacks were developed [21]. The complete attack has a certain series of steps, and its behavior is more easily predictable if we take as a relevant characteristic the scenario or day to which it belongs. For this analysis we took some relevant features in network traffic such as: IP source and destination addresses, destination and source ports, total bytes per flow, mean bytes per flow, flow duration and TCP flags.

A. Source and destination IP addresses

Source and destination IP addresses can be some of the most relevant features because it allows identifying the devices transmitting anomalous traffic on the network. Figure 1 shows how these addresses are distributed taking into account that they are divided into broadcast, multicast, unknown (0.0.0.0/8), private network addresses and WAN (containing all the public addresses). For a better visualization of the features, a normalization by tag has been performed. This way, the sum of the seven attack bars is 100%, and the same for the normal bars.

Figure 1 indicates the distribution of both normal and attack flows over the different IP source addresses. More than 60% of anomalous traffic comes from two of the local networks (192.168.1.0 and 192.168.2.0).

The network 192.168.5.0 consists of web, email, DNS, and NAT servers and it gives access to the Internet. Figure 2 shows the distribution of both normal and attack flows over the different IP destination networks. Most of the attack traffic, around 70%, is destined to the lately mentioned network. The attack flows with broadcast, multicast, unknown and WAN destination addresses represent the minority of anomalous traffic.

Therefore, determining the source and destination addresses can be important to predict the type of traffic.

B. Source and destination ports

Some ports are commonly used by some kind of specific services, while others are for public use. The analysis of the data was done making the classification of the ports by well known ports (port numbers below 1024), registered ports (port

Fig. 1. Source address statistics.

numbers between 1024 and 49151) and private ports (port numbers greater than 49152).

Figure 3 shows the distribution of source ports, where more than 60% of the source ports used, both in attack and normal flows, are registered ports, and the minority of ports are well known ports. On the other hand, Figure 4 depicts the distribution of destination ports. Unlike source ports, most are well known ports, and the least used ports are the private ones.

C. Mean bytes

The type of protocol used and the direction in the transmission can help us distinguish the type of traffic we are dealing with. Table II presents the minimum and maximum values, the median and the mean of the mean bytes by flow, by protocol and global. Due to the dispersion of the data, the descriptive analysis regarding means does not yield important conclusions, but it helps us identify flow behaviors. Consequently, the

Fig. 2. Destination address statistics.

Fig. 3. Source port statistics.

Fig. 4. Destination port statistics.

Fig. 5. Mean bytes by direction and protocol.

median together with the minimum and the maximum allow us to better understand the distribution of the data over the feature.

With respect to the ICMP protocol the vast majority of attacks have an average of 51 to 100 bytes, while for normal traffic most flows are distributed between 101 and 200 bytes on average. Anyway, the percentage of flows with mean bytes between 51 and 100 is considerable. For UDP, despite finding the flows distributed in an average between 51 and 500, a little more than 60% have an average between 201 and 500 bytes per flow. The distribution of normal traffic is similar. However,

most flows for normal traffic are between 101 and 200 mean bytes. For TCP the distribution of normal traffic is divided almost uniformly in the range of between 51 and 1000 mean bytes. On the other hand for the attack traffic we find that more than half of the TCP flows have a mean size between 501 and 1000 bytes.

Likewise, the direction is a relevant feature for the analysis. It can take different values: local to local (L2L), local to remote (L2R) or remote to local (R2L). Figure 5 shows a Box and Whisker plot representing the mean size by protocol and direction. This graph demonstrates that UDP has a greater dispersion in terms of the average number of bytes in normal traffic. It is important to highlight the large number of outliers presented.

The normal traffic flows have different sizes, with flows up to 1000 bytes on average. However, more than 40% are

TABLE II
MEAN BYTES STATISTICS.

	TCP		UDP		ICMP		Global
	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	Attack	Normal	
Min	64	64	96	64	64	64	64
Median	551.02	218.8	247	167.5	64	104	196
Max	1062.64	1518	374.33	2149.5	181	594	2149.5
Mean	400.85	348.96	234.22	185.07	68.32	119.93	316

TABLE III
DURATION STATISTICS.

	Normal	Attack	Global
Min	0	0	0
Max	49,136	15,126	49,136
Mean	53.71	3.71	51.92
Median	1	1	1

located between 51 and 100 bytes. L2R flows means are distributed over the range of between 51 and 1000 bytes. However, we find normal flows with average bytes above 1000 bytes. Among the R2L flows, we find flows from 51 to 1000 bytes. Finally, most L2L attack streams have between 501 and 1000 bytes. On the other hand, more than 35% of the flows have between 51 and 100 bytes. Attack flows with an average of more than 1000 bytes are negligible in relation to other flow sizes.

D. Duration

In terms of duration, minimum, maximum, mean and median values were considered, as shown in Table III. From these values, a threshold of 60 seconds separating long-term flows from short-term ones can be set. In addition, the median results indicate that 50% of flows last a second or less.

E. Flags

For this analysis the number of TCP protocol flows sent by a given control flag, both source and destination, is determined. There are a total of 1,928,942 flows, and 1,522,990 correspond to TCP flows. The largest number of flags used were A flags with 1,477,118 source flags and 1,440,596 destination flags as shown in Table IV. All the U flags sent were in attack flows while in destination there were no U flags. The highest percentage of attack destination flags were the R flags with 10,95%, while in source flags just 1,46% of these were sent.

Moreover, it is not only relevant to study flags individually but also to study the combinations of the flags. For instance, regarding the attack flows, 62,55% have F, S, P, A as source flags and F, S, P, A as destination flags; 27,2158% have a S as source flag and R, A as destination flags; the 2.35% of the anomalous traffic have S, A as source flags and S,A as destination flags; 2,099% have S as source flag; and 1,689% have F, S, P, A as source flags and F, S, R, A as destination flags.

IV. MODEL

In this paper we present an approach where flow information released with the ISCX dataset is grouped defining superflows, that is, similar flows are classified together creating clusters. This clustering is made using a SOM, maintaining a 30 by 30 dimension as in the work presented in [14]. It is important to remark that flows belonging to the same cluster share the same classification tag (all are normal or attack).

Our main purpose is to process the flows and classify the superflow into normal or attack. Therefore we formalize this problem as a binary classification problem. In fact, we define a machine learning problem taking into account the features analyzed in Section III. As the information about the flows contained in a cluster is received, this information is processed and aggregated so as to make a decision about the classification of the superflow. For doing this, we opt for the RF algorithm [4]. We provide the RF with the clusters obtained from the SOM.

Compared with other commonly known machine-learning methods, RF models are suitable because they have some advantages: (i) low training time complexity, and fast prediction; (ii) resilience to deal with imbalanced datasets; (iii) embedded feature selection method and intrinsic metrics to rank features by importance; and (iv) able to deal natively with categorical and continuous features. The RF model is an ensemble of Decision Trees, which may be used for classification or regression. The prediction in the classification case is based on the majority votes of the predicted values using the Decision Trees, and in the regression case, the result is the average of the outcomes of the trees. On the training phase, for each tree is produced a training set considering the samples in the original training set, and, to create each tree split, it is randomly selected a set of features, which are then evaluated by a measure to define which one should produce the split. This randomness provides different trees, which usually achieve better prediction performance combined [19].

V. FEATURES

Following, we describe the variants for the model along with their configurations. Starting with the types of features analyzed in Section III, we create the model and we study how feature engineering can help us improve the results. We have divided the features into several groups: address, bytes, day, direction, duration, flags, port, protocol and time.

- *Address*. For every superflow we create two features indicating the most repeated source and destination IP

TABLE IV
FLAGS STATISTICS.

	Source			Destination		
	Attack	Normal	Total flows	Attack	Normal	Total flows
A	3.24%	96.76%	1,477,118	4.61%	95.39%	1,440,596
F	3.29%	96.41%	1,243,559	3.54 %	96.46%	1,269,753
R	1.46%	98.54 %	41,651	10.95%	89.05%	183,915
S	5.03%	94.97%	1,334,490	3.62%	96.38%	1,294,202
P	3.43%	96.57%	1,319,183	3.36%	96.64%	1,308,577
U	100%	0%	24	0%	0%	0
None	0.39%	99.61%	3,063	3.18%	96.82%	62,537

addresses, but taking into account the values considered in Section III: the five private network addresses class C, multicast, broadcast, WAN and unknown. The latter is used when source or destination belongs to the network 0.0.0.0/8. It is important to note that the library employed presents a restriction regarding the number of levels in a category or factor (only 32). Therefore, it was not possible to consider individual IP addresses, since the overall amount of values is much higher than 32.

- *Bytes*. In order to capture the differences in the frame size in every superflow, we have defined four features for source and four for destination, resulting in a minimum, a maximum, a mean and a median of the mean frame size indicated for each flow.
- *Day*. A feature identifies the most repeated day of beginning for the flows in a particular superflow.
- *Direction*. As we have concluded that the direction of the communication provides relevant information, we have also defined a feature indicating the most numerous direction in the superflow.
- *Duration*. Five different features have been created related to the duration of the flows. The first four are minimum, maximum, mean and median. Finally, the fifth one indicates if the most part of the flows lasts more than 60 seconds or not.
- *Flags*. As explained previously, the presence of particular TCP flags can determine a decision about the classification of a particular flow. This is the reason why we have defined two different features for every flag: the first one indicates if there exists a flow with the particular flag belonging to the superflow, and the other indicates if the majority of the flows in the superflow present this flag. Since source and destination flags are different, and considering that in the dataset there are F, S, R, P, U and A flags [1], we have obtained a total of 24 features.
- *Port*. In the same way that we defined two features for the IP addresses, we have also defined two features (source and destination ports) taking into account the most repeated values explained in Section III: well-known, registered and private.
- *Protocol*. Although most part of the traffic is TCP, it is relevant to mark those superflows where UDP or ICMP

traffic is present. This way we have defined three features representing the presence of ICMP, TCP and UDP traffic in the superflow.

- *Time*. Regarding time, four features have been considered: two of them establish the most popular start and stop hours in the superflow, and the remaining ones the most popular start and stop hour interval, being these intervals 0-7, 8-15 and 16-23.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

We decide to employ the RF algorithm for classifying. According to this, we have chosen the implementation found in the *randomForest* package for R [12].

The approach we followed for constructing the training set is to select a percentage of the available flows (80%). The evaluation subset consists of the remaining flows (20%).

Regarding the RF variables, we have chosen a *mtry* equals to 10 and a *ntree* equals to 500. The first one represents the number of variables selected by the algorithm from the set of predictors available. That is, considering a Decision Tree, the algorithm randomly chooses a *mtry* number of variables, rather than doing an exhaustive search over all the possible variables to determine which is the best for doing every split. As for *ntree*, it is the number of Decision Trees forming the Random Forest.

Typically, the output of a RF is one of the categories considered (in our case: normal or attack). In order to implement the possibility of delaying the response, we employ an acceptance threshold. We tried selecting the following values: 0.5, 0.7 and 0.9. The ratio of trees with the same vote must be greater than the acceptance threshold so that the RF provides a definitive response. In other case, the response is delayed at least up to the reception of more information.

The variables of the RF are those explained in Section V. Different experiments have been performed to determine the importance of the variables and the best setup. We considered ten variants according to the type of features dropped from the model: address, bytes, day, direction, duration, flags, port, protocol, time and nothing. The last one represents the alternative where all the features are employed. The results have been evaluated using different metrics: the traditional precision, recall and F1, and Early Risk Detection Error (ERDE) [15].

A. ERDE

The ERDE metric [15] is devoted to Information Retrieval, but it can be very useful for Computer Networks too. Using this metric, the evaluation considers not only the correctness of the output (that is, the precision) but also the delay taken to emit its decision.

In our case the ERDE for a superflow is calculated as it is explained in Equation 1, where d is the delay (the number of flows needed to make a decision); o is the parameter for the ERDE metric; TP is the number of True Positive cases, that is, superflows correctly classified as attack; TN is the number of True Negative cases, or superflows correctly classified as normal; FP (False Positive cases) are those superflows classified as attack when they are normal traffic; and, finally, FN (False Negative cases) are those superflows marked as normal when they are attack traffic.

$$ERDE_o = \begin{cases} \frac{TP}{|superflows|} & \text{if } FP \\ 1 & \text{if } FN \\ 1 - \frac{1}{1+e^{d-o}} & \text{if } TP \\ 0 & \text{if } TN \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The overall error would be the mean of the ERDE values computed for each superflow.

B. Methodology

In order to represent the progressive arrival of the data, we define a test stage consisting of different and disjunct releases or chunks of data. The data will be provided to the algorithm ordered by time. The flows belonging to the same superflow will be equally distributed among the chunks. This way, the lesser the number of flows needed for determining the right tag (normal or attack) for a superflow, the better the ERDE obtained. Once the decision is made, it cannot be changed. However, when the model cannot classify a superflow considering the data received and it proposes a delay, the model can try to classify again when the next chunk is available. So, the delay is proposed when the model has not enough information in order to give a final response.

We provide the results for two numbers of chunks, 10 and 100, in order to describe how the model and the metric behave according to the number of flows per chunk.

Regarding the parameter o we have evaluated the model using $ERDE_5$ and $ERDE_{50}$.

C. Results

Table V shows the results obtained by the *Oracle* algorithm at each chunk. Oracle represents the algorithm which classifies perfectly every superflow. Depending on the chunk where the algorithm makes the classification, we use different names. For example, Oracle 3 is the algorithm which proposes a delay after chunks 1 and 2, and classify correctly all the superflows after having received the information contained in chunk 3. For the sake of clarity, results from Oracle 11 to Oracle 100 are not shown when 100 chunks are considered.

TABLE V
ORACLE RESULTS FOR CHUNKS 1 TO 10 CONSIDERING 10 AND 100
CHUNKS.

	10 chunks		100 chunks	
	$ERDE_5$	$ERDE_{50}$	$ERDE_5$	$ERDE_{50}$
Oracle 1	7.96%	5.17%	5.19%	1.80%
Oracle 2	9.02%	6.03%	6.35%	1.80%
Oracle 3	9.45%	6.04%	6.52%	2.46%
Oracle 4	9.48%	6.90%	6.79%	2.70%
Oracle 5	9.48%	7.75%	7.21%	3.60%
Oracle 6	9.48%	7.76%	7.62%	3.60%
Oracle 7	9.48%	7.76%	7.89%	3.60%
Oracle 8	9.48%	7.76%	8.02%	3.82%
Oracle 9	9.48%	7.76%	8.08%	5.37%
Oracle 10	9.48%	9.48%	8.10%	5.41%

These algorithms obtain perfect values for precision, recall and F1 (that is, 1.0), because they do not commit any mistake in their proposals. However, ERDE metrics are much more demanding, specially $ERDE_5$. The reason is that every true positive decision made after the fifth flow is penalized, and this penalization increases as more flows are necessary. When using less chunks, there are more flows by chunk, so in many cases it will not be possible to decide correctly before having received the fifth flow, since the mean number of flows by superflows is about 4,000. So, the fact that some superflows will have more than 5 flows in the first chunk makes an early prediction impossible. The same conclusion can be obtained comparing the results in Table V for 10 chunks and 100 chunks. Nevertheless the ERDE metric focuses on an important perspective: it gives relevance to the fact that the classification must be done as soon as possible, what fits very well typical computer networks needs. In fact, it gives little importance to correct detection of attacks if this detection is done after having processed many flows.

In some cases in Table V values are repeated along several rows, such as 9.48. This repetition is motivated by the fact previously mentioned: the penalization induced when there is a delay in the decision. Indeed, it is also noticeable that the number of flows by chunk is usually higher than the value of o parameter. So, true positive becomes almost a false negative since the value for the ERDE is around 1 for the superflows in this situation.

Figures 6 and 7 depict the results for our model taking into account the ERDE metric. The best results are shown when the acceptance threshold is 0.5, and the worst ones when the threshold is 0.9. The main reason is that in many cases the model is not capable of making a decision because there is not enough votes for exceeding the threshold. However, with a lower threshold like 0.5 the decision is made rapidly because only a tie in votes would produce that the decision was a delay. Having superflows containing so many flows, the model has enough information to classify after the first chunk.

On the other hand, Figures 8 and 9 focus on the classic metrics. With respect to precision we obtained great results.

Fig. 6. ERDE results for the model removing different classes of information using ten chunks.

Fig. 8. Classic metrics results for the model removing different classes of information using 10 chunks.

Fig. 7. ERDE results for the model removing different classes of information using 100 chunks.

However, the recall is not as good. In fact, despite obtaining the best precision results with threshold equals to 0.9, the worst recall results appear with this threshold. In this case the model only makes a decision if it has many evidences of that. As for F1, the best threshold is 0.5 when only ten chunks are used, and 0.7 when a hundred of chunks are employed.

It is remarkable the behavior of the model without time features, since it is not capable of classifying correctly any attack superflow. This is related to the fact that attacks are very located in time in the original dataset.

A paradigmatic case is found when dropping bytes information. Using 0.5 as the threshold, results are particularly good not only for the ERDE metric, but also for precision, recall and F1. This can indicate that there are too many features related to size information and the model is somehow biased towards this kind of features.

The same is happening with flag information. Although from the analysis we conclude the relevance of some features, saturating the model with a type of features is not adequate.

Anyway it is also appreciable that the alternative where no feature is dropped (*nothing*) reaches very good results taking into account all the metrics.

Comparing our model with the Oracle models, some great results appear. We observe that our best performing model on the $ERDE_5$ metric with 10 chunks is equivalent to *Oracle 1*, and with 100 chunks is better than *Oracle 2* and worse than *Oracle 1*. In addition, our best performing model on $ERDE_{50}$ metric with 10 chunks is better than *Oracle 2* and slightly worse than *Oracle 1*. Moreover, with 100 chunks our best $ERDE_{50}$ result (3.60) is analogous to *Oracle 5*.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper we tackled a thorough flow-based analysis of a public IDS dataset. This analysis resulted in information about the features available.

On the other hand, we presented a feature-based approach based on the analysis in order to setup a RF model. This

Fig. 9. Classic metrics results for the model removing different classes of information using 100 chunks.

model demonstrated very good results in classifying traffic not only accurately but also in a rapid way. In the domain of the problem proposed (the intrusion detection based on anomaly detection) time is a critical factor to minimize the impact of an attack. Due to these circumstances, we propose the use of the ERDE, a metric that has been successfully employed for early risk detection in other domains.

In the near future we plan to extend this work in several ways. First, we will deal with a more resource-consuming approach taking into account the payload packet inspection. Second, we would like to analyze other machine-learning algorithms and deep learning approaches, since we think that ERDE metric can lead to promising conclusions.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness of Spain (Project TIN2015-70648-P), by the Xunta de Galicia (Centro singular de investigación de Galicia accreditation 2016-2019) and the European Union (European Regional Development Fund - ERDF).

REFERENCES

- [1] "Transmission Control Protocol," RFC 793, Sep. 1981. [Online]. Available: <https://rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc793.txt>
- [2] S. Adibi, "Traffic Classification Packet-, Flow-, and Application-based Approaches," *IJACSA - International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 1, pp. 6–15, 2010.
- [3] R. Bace and P. Mell, "NIST Special Publication on Intrusion Detection Systems," 2001.
- [4] L. Breiman, "Random forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, 2001.

- [5] C. del Coso, D. Fustes, C. Dafonte, F. J. Nóvoa, J. M. Rodríguez-Pedreira, and B. Arcay, "Mixing numerical and categorical data in a self-organizing map by means of frequency neurons," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 36, pp. 246–254, nov 2015.
- [6] G. Dong and H. Liu, *Feature Engineering for Machine Learning and Data Analytics*, 1st ed. CRC Press, 2018.
- [7] P. García-Teodoro, J. Díaz-Verdejo, G. Maciá-Fernández, and E. Vázquez, "Anomaly-based network intrusion detection: Techniques, systems and challenges," *Computers & Security*, vol. 28, no. 1-2, pp. 18–28, feb 2009.
- [8] A. Grover and J. Leskovec, "node2vec," in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining SIGKDD 2016*. ACM Press, 2016.
- [9] H. S. Hota and A. K. Shrivastava, "Data mining approach for developing various models based on types of attack and feature selection as intrusion detection systems (IDS)," in *Intelligent Computing, Networking, and Informatics*. Springer India, dec 2013, pp. 845–851.
- [10] E. Kim and S. Kim, "A novel hierarchical detection method for enhancing anomaly detection efficiency," in *2015 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks (CICN)*. IEEE, dec 2015.
- [11] B. Li, J. Springer, G. Bebis, and M. Hadi Gunes, "Review: A survey of network flow applications," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 567–581, Mar. 2013.
- [12] A. Liaw and M. Wiener, "Classification and regression by randomforest," *R News*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 18–22, 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/doc/Rnews/>
- [13] H. Lin, Z. Yan, Y. Chen, and L. Zhang, "A survey on network security-related data collection technologies," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 18 345–18 365, 2018.
- [14] M. F. Lopez-Vizcaino, C. Dafonte, F. J. Novoa, D. Garabato, M. Alvarez, and D. Fernandez, "Network data flow clustering based on unsupervised learning," in *Under review*, 2018.
- [15] D. E. Losada and F. Crestani, "A test collection for research on depression and language use," in *Conference Labs of the Evaluation Forum*. Springer, 2016, pp. 28–39.
- [16] L. M. Ibrahim, D. T. Basheer, and M. S. Mahmood, "A comparison study for intrusion database (kdd99, nsl-kdd) based on self organization map (som) artificial neural network," vol. 8, pp. 107–119, 02 2013.
- [17] S. Masarat, S. Sharifian, and H. Taheri, "Modified parallel random forest for intrusion detection systems," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 2235–2258, may 2016.
- [18] V. K. Pachghare, P. Kulkarni, and D. M. Nikam, "Intrusion detection system using self organizing maps," in *2009 International Conference on Intelligent Agent & Multi-Agent Systems*. IEEE, jul 2009.
- [19] P. A. A. Resende and A. C. Drummond, "A survey of random forest based methods for intrusion detection systems," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 1–36, may 2018.
- [20] R. Sadre, A. Sperotto, R. Hofstede, and N. Brownlee, "Flow-based approaches in network management: Recent advances and future trends," *Netw.*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 219–220, Jul. 2014.
- [21] A. Shiravi, H. Shiravi, M. Tavallaei, and A. A. Ghorbani, "Toward developing a systematic approach to generate benchmark datasets for intrusion detection," *Comput. Secur.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 357–374, May 2012.
- [22] C. So-In, "A survey of network traffic monitoring and analysis tools," 2006.
- [23] C. R. Turner, A. L. Wolf, A. Fuggetta, and L. Lavazza, "Feature engineering," in *Proceedings of the 9th International Workshop on Software Specification and Design*, ser. IWSSD '98. Washington, DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society, 1998, pp. 162–.
- [24] M. F. Umer, M. Sher, and Y. Bi, "Flow-based intrusion detection: Techniques and challenges," *Computers & Security*, vol. 70, pp. 238–254, sep 2017.
- [25] M. Yin, D. Yao, J. Luo, X. Liu, and J. Ma, "Network backbone anomaly detection using double random forests based on non-extensive entropy feature extraction," in *2013 Ninth International Conference on Natural Computation (ICNC)*. IEEE, jul 2013.
- [26] D. Zhou, Z. Yan, Y. Fu, and Z. Yao, "A survey on network data collection," *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*, vol. 116, pp. 9–23, aug 2018.